

Innovative India: Science & Technology Review. L. K. Sharma and Sima Sharma (eds). Medialand, London, ISBN: 0 9534981 0 7. Case bound. 1999. 350 pp. Price not known.

This book on India's achievements in science and technology in the past fifty years is more a coffee table book than a critical assessment. Sponsored by government agencies such as the Department of Biotechnology and Videsh Sanchar Nigam as well as by corporate giants such as Indian Oil, Reliance Industries Limited, and Hindustan Lever Limited, it is designed to promote modern India, says the publisher's note, and it is intended to reach 'buyers and sellers of technology and those planning to site their research in India'.

Released in time for the World Conference on Science for the 21st century, that took place in Budapest during 26 June–1 July 1999, this neatly-bound volume gives the reader an overview of the many successful projects and some lesser known but equally important scientific achievements of India. The more than 90 articles cover virtually every field in which India has invested in the recent past – agriculture, astronomy, atomic energy, aeronautics and space science, biotechnology, computers, defence research, electronics, information and communication technologies, medical research, oceanography, energy research and so on. Although there is considerable variation in the depth of coverage and style of presentation, as is to be expected in a collection of this kind, many of these articles can be taken to be authentic as they are written by people who actually managed important programmes and projects. The editors have persuaded most of India's leaders of science – some of them currently active, e.g. C. N. R. Rao and M. S. Swaminathan – to contribute to this volume. The list of contributors include many past and present heads of Government of India's science departments, past presidents of Academies of Science, policy makers, a few captains of industry, diplomats, a few foreign scientists, several technocrats, a couple of journalists and some officers of science-related ministries of the Government of India. Unfortunately, the affiliations of some authors are not given. A notable inclusion is N. Raghuram, who

only about two years ago came in for considerable criticism from the S&T establishment for what he and co-author Madhavi wrote on the decline of Indian science, in terms of numbers of papers published in refereed journals, in a brief note in *Nature*. Actually, Raghuram has contributed two articles to this volume, one on the Giant Meterwave Radio Telescope and the other on the National Chemical Laboratory, Pune. Predictably, there is nothing in these two articles that can invite the wrath of the custodians of Indian science!

Apart from NCL, other institutions profiled include Raman Research Institute, Saha Institute, M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation, SAIL, Hindustan Lever, BHEL, and Reddy's Laboratories. There is a 4-page write up on the Department of Biotechnology: highlights. It seems to have been lifted from a brochure of the department without editing.

I was impressed by some candid statements. Here are a few examples. Gifted with world-class intellectual and other resources, we are unable to manage them well, says Roddam Narasimha, and pleads for internal liberalization of science and technology. 'Why does Indian science and technology have so little observable impact on the national economy?' asks P. Rama Rao, and pleads for strengthening university research. He is in excellent company. Hermann Bondi observes 'many university departments have little time, energy or facilities for research'.

Apart from recounting the achievements of Indian science, the book offers two sections – one called 'View from afar', wherein some eminent foreign scientists give their impressions, and the other on 'International co-operation' that covers scientific co-operation with USA, UK, Germany and France. There is also a brief section on our scientific heritage and a two-page note on technology exports. But there is no index.

As I read through the book, I could not help asking myself why a book trying to sell Indian technology could not have been printed and published in India. Or for that matter, why is it that the indigenously developed wireless local loop technology, about which Ashok Jhunjhunwala has written so lucidly, is not yet widely used in the country? Is it for the same reason that the process for the production of silicon developed by

Vasudevamurthy and Suryan of the Indian Institute of Science was dumped in favour of Hemlock's technology in the early eighties?

I got the feeling that although the editors devoted much time in collecting and putting together the volume, at the end they had to finish the job in a hurry.

I am not sure if the publisher's ambition, viz. reaching out to potential buyers abroad of Indian technology, will be fulfilled, but I recommend that the sponsors distribute this book widely within India – not only to college and university libraries but also to schools and public libraries. Our countrymen, especially students and the lay public, ought to know about our achievements in science and technology and many of these achievements are narrated here.

SUBBIAH ARUNACHALM

*M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation,
3rd Cross Street,
Taramani Institutional Area,
Chennai 600 013, India*

Reconstruction or Destruction? Science and Technology at Stake in Transition Economies. Claes Brundenius, Bo Göransson and Prasada Reddy. Universities Press (India) Limited, Hyderabad. ISBN: 81 7371 200 X. Paperback. 1999. 260 pp. Price: Rs 550.

This book is a compilation of revised and edited contributions by a dozen participants in a workshop at the Research Policy Institute, Lund University, Sweden, 6–8 June 1996, entitled *Economic Restructuring with Equity and Competitiveness – Implications for Science and Technology Policies*. The countries in focus at the workshop were nine 'former Centrally Planned Economies (CPEs); Three former Soviet Republics (Russia, Belarus and Ukraine); three Eastern European countries (the Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia) and three 'Third World Economies' (China, Cuba and Vietnam)'. The contributors are from these countries in focus (except China) and from Scandinavia. Their contributions deal with the 'transition (in these

countries) from plan to market . . . with an emphasis on implications for Science and Technology policies'.

As the Preface notes: 'This transition has been, and in most countries still is, quite painful. The restructuring of the economies, as a result of globalisation, the demise of the Soviet Union and their abandoning the "command" economy strategy, *has not yielded the results that many had expected in the West. Even in a growth economy like China, the transition to market economy has implied serious social problems and widening income gaps*'. And, as shown in the introductory chapter, *the Russian depression is unprecedented in history, both with regard to length and depth*. (Italicization by reviewer).

The 'Introduction' by Claes Brundenius of the Centre for Development Research, Denmark, gets to the nub of the 'problematique' of the Soviet model. 'In Soviet strategic economic thinking there was an obsession with fulfillment of quantitative goals (with little or no consideration of quality) through capital extension, or 'widening', rather than increasing capital intensity, 'deepening'. . . . Growth rates were impressive during the first five-year plans and in the immediate reconstruction after the war. But technology and organization of work were based on mass-scale Ford assembly line principles and with technology to a large extent imported, or imitated, from the West, and the model was then exported to Eastern Europe and many developing countries. (Including India – reviewer).

Lenin had, like the czars, been a great admirer of Western technological advances and he firmly believed that the combination of Western technology and the communist principles of planning and social relations would provide an invincible formula for eternal Soviet superiority.

Large-scale production with enormous concentration of power in huge state monopolies and trusts, *modelled after the US monopoly capitalism of the 1920s*, (italicization by reviewer) was the ideal for organization of the state-owned production units in the USSR.

The main problem with this strategy was that it was based on a static view of technological change (as well as of capitalist development). The Soviet model of accumulation was . . . based on

energy- and resource-intensive technologies. *It is true that this was also the case in the West* (italicization by reviewer) but in the Soviet centrally planned economy . . . it was more problematic since there were no checks on imbalances in the system – such as waste and depletion of resources, pollution and other environmental costs. So when the bill came to the West in 1973 – in the form of quadrupled energy prices – for decades of ruthless exploitation (by the West) of energy and raw material resources, it (the bill) gave clear signals for the system to change and to initiate 'the painful transition to a new technological paradigm'.

In contrast, no such signals were perceived in the Soviet system. For decades it had been assumed that crises, such as recessions and depressions, had been phenomena typical of capitalism'.

In other words, the Soviet industrial-economic collapse was caused by uncorrected systemic ossification, not by a wrong post-Russian Revolution (1917) choice of development model, which US-inspired model (what irony!) sought to emulate, in much shorter development-time, the consumption patterns and living styles of the West. The systemic ossification of the 'command economy', although recognized quite early-on in its coming by the Soviet S&T community, remained uncorrected because the Soviet 'command polity' was regressive (indeed cruelly repressive in the Stalinist era) and paralysed by Marxist–Leninist dogma, continuing loyalty to which was engendered by its successful projection as having won for the Soviets release from tsarist despotism. That dogma had, ironically, been itself rendered obsolete by rapid Fordist industrial development enabled by the exertions of scientists and technologists of the Soviet Union. This form of development had been 'used-up', so to speak, in the post-war (re)construction of the Soviet Union accomplished at great human cost in the face of an implacably hostile West. So, ' . . . when *perestroika* and *glasnost* came with Gorbachev in 1986, it was simply too late to modify a system that had long been obsolete'.

Economists pontificate on, and prescribe policies for, the one crucial factor of production (S&T) they self-confessedly do not understand. Professional economists both from within and

outside the governments they advise have a lot to answer for the collective miseries of whole nations and their peoples. The Nobel Prize in economics is (justifiably) something of a joke amongst natural scientists. Actually, it is a cruel joke; several of the winners have propounded theories which, when put into practice, ostensibly to improve the lot of peoples, have been the major cause of their worsening poverty. Thus the application of the counter-dogmas of the 'Washington Consensus' to the post-Soviet industrial economies of the Centrally Planned Economies (CPEs) has resulted in an S&T tragedy: 'With the transition to market economy, that in many CPEs was unnecessarily sudden and drastic (shock therapy), thousands of S&T personnel have abandoned (or are being forced to abandon) their professions as researchers. In some cases this has no doubt been a painful but necessary downsizing process. In many cases, however, the reason has not been the need for downsizing as such, but purely economic. The state does not have the financial resources for the simple reason that it does not prioritize R&D, which is likely to be a fatal mistake. This means that in many of these countries, primarily in the former Soviet Union, we are witnessing great potential going down the drain and it will take at least a generation to build up such a highly qualified scientific base again'.

Such systemic destruction of the scientific potential of the CPEs cannot really be explained except as the Western follow-through to the defeat of the Soviet Union in the Cold War. What the contributors to this volume have not addressed (gingerly side-stepped?) is the fact that the S&T capabilities of the former Soviet Union and its 'dependent territories' of the CPEs have been systematically and deliberately brought down and destroyed as the final denouement of the Cold War, so that these capabilities may never again contribute to the military strength of these countries, except as supportive adjuncts to, and under the watchful control of, an eastwardly expanded NATO.

The exception is, of course, China. Too big, too talented, too experienced, too tightly controlled (internally), absolutely single-minded in its pursuit of economic and military power, the biggest non-member of WTO, a veto-wielding permanent member of the United Nations

Security Council, a Nuclear Weapons State with a nuclear reach that extends to the continental United States, China is clearly a case apart. I am surprised the organizers of the Lund Workshop did not realize that China is so out-of-line on every parameter with the other cases considered as to suggest a mistake in its inclusion as a case; a mistake compounded by the absence of a contribution from a mainland Chinese.

Since only some of the contributions deal with the agricultural or medical components of the S&T systems in the CPE countries considered, the title of this compilation should have been '*Industrial Science and Technology at Stake...*'. But shed a tear for this:

'In the late 1960s and the 1970s, Hungarian agriculture, due to its innovative development, was among the leading European countries in the productivity indexes of its 42 products. The paradigm of technological development in Hungarian agriculture, with its innovative entrepreneurial values and system approach, at that time was basically different from that of the industry. It was limited, but entrepreneurship in the management of agricultural cooperatives and state farms was allowed, while the industrial management was deprived of it. The scarcity of resources, the industrial management blocking investment in agricultural sector, and the crisis of the whole economy stopped and even retarded the innovative development of agriculture in the second part of the 1980s. The loss of its Eastern market, and the excessively inappropriate governmental agricultural policy at the beginning of the 1990s, finally knocked out this once prospering sector of economy. After 1992, one third or half of the agricultural organizations were forced to use horses and manual power instead of machines...'

At Rs 550, this paperback is at the margin of the reach of individual S&T policy-wallahs but worth the buy if your calling requires you to counter in real-time smart-alec free-marketeers peddling the 'Washington Consensus', and/or smarter-alec economists of Marxist-Leninist persuasion.

V. SIDDHARTHA

51 Bharati Nagar,
New Delhi 110 003, India

Sustainable Agriculture – Towards an Evergreen Revolution. M. S. Swaminathan. Konark Publishers Pvt. Ltd, A-149, Main Vikas Marg, Delhi 110 092, India. 1999. 219 pp. Price: Rs 250.

M. S. Swaminathan has a number of articles and addresses to his credit. This book includes among others 'Our Agricultural Future', the Sardar Patel Memorial Lecture which he delivered in 1973. I have admired this lecture from the time I read it in October 1973. I believe this lecture should be the reading material for all those who wish to graduate in agriculture in India. The lecture was written when there was enthusiasm of 'Green Revolution', and yet he decided to talk about the Assets and Liabilities in agriculture in India. We talk today of soil and water degradation, but he cautioned about it 25 years ago. He wrote about 'Ecological Seasons' and I quote something which should have been practiced. 'In Assam, the period between September and May is free from floods, since the major floods have either taken place in May-June or more commonly in August. There is tremendous potential in this area for exploiting groundwater and for arranging for lift irrigation. An assured *rabi* crop can be raised if arrangements can be made to supply water.' I wonder if the State Government and planners took note of this prognosis, though all politicians and bureaucrats talk of improving the economy of North-east.

Writing about fruit crops, the address goes to identify: 'The concept of population explosion in fields has also permeated horticulture. Growingly, emphasis is being placed in orchards on the selection of dwarfing root stocks. Some experts believe that fruit orchards of the future may be "Lilliputian" in nature, facilitating high management efficiency.' And yet even today we have mostly low population orchards with low productivity. The horticulturists or plant scientists could have brought a remarkable change if his advice was taken by the masters of horticulture.

The lecture also emphasized the importance of biological control of pests, economy through recycling and reducing post-harvest losses, which Swaminathan saw as the emerging needs of Indian agriculture. Unfortunately, even today

the biological control of pests remains a laboratory exercise, and we cannot claim that we have it operating even in half a million hectare area out of approximately 200 million gross cropped area. Will the private sector be able to make biological control and IPM as common acceptable practices? A thrust has been given to the post-harvest technology, but we hardly have well-researched and quantified data on losses of the various vegetables and fruits in different regions of the country. We do know that in one region or other tomatoes are wasted because of over production. There is hardly any good science in relation to pre-harvest and post-harvest technology in different fruits and vegetables. Is it because the basic sciences have remained outside the realm of agriculture? Swaminathan has been a promoter of basic sciences in agriculture, but others did not follow the path charted out by him.

India frequently faces droughts and unfavourable weather, but being a large country we have good weather in some region or the other every year. With the exception of one or two instances, the whole country has never experienced bad weather. Hence, there is the importance of 'Good Weather Code', as stated in the first chapter. Could we take full advantage of a good weather in a given year? In 1973, when this lecture was written, the means of communication and transport were limited, but today this kind of code could become a vehicle of change and prosperity of the country in the next millennium.

Now, many agriculture scientists would like agriculture to be taught from the primary school level. However, Swaminathan says: 'During the early years of childhood, before the child begins to receive formal education, and in primary school, the major emphasis should be on living in nature and with nature, learning about nature through direct observation, and using the materials provided in nature to develop scientific skills, aptitude and habits of thought'.

The first chapter also counts floristic diversity and animal wealth as important assets. It was this vision of Swaminathan which led to the establishment of such institutions as National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, National Bureau of Animal Genetic Resources and National Bureau of Fish Resources. While the collections of plant resources have been